

Electrodynamic forces driving DNA-protein interactions at large biomolecular distances

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Abstract

In the present paper we address the general problem of selective electrodynamic interactions between DNA and protein, which have been motivated by decades of theoretical study and very recent experimental findings (M. Lechelon et al, *Sci Adv* **8**, eab15855 (2022)). Signatures of such partnerships between the two broad classes of biomolecules have been obtained by applying the so-called resonant recognition model (RRM). Inspired by the Davydov and Holstein-Fröhlich models describing electron motion along biomolecules, and using a model Hamiltonian written in second quantization, the time-dependent variational principle (TDVP) is used to derive the dynamical equations of the system. We demonstrate the efficacy of this second-quantized RRM for a well-documented biochemical system consisting of a restriction enzyme, *EcoRI*, which binds selectively to a palindromic six-base-pair target within a DNA oligonucleotide sequence to catalyze a DNA double-strand cleavage. The time-domain Fourier spectra of the electron currents numerically computed for the DNA fragment and for the *EcoRI* enzyme, respectively, exhibit a cross-correlation spectrum with a sharp co-resonance peak. When the target DNA recognition sequence is randomized, this sharp co-resonance peak is replaced with a broad and noisy spectrum. Such a sequence-dependent charge transfer phenomenology is suggestive of a potentially rich variety of selective electrodynamic interactions influencing the coordinated activity of DNA substrates, enzymes, transcription factors, ligands, and other proteins under realistic biochemical conditions characterized by electron-phonon excitations.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Progress in molecular and cellular biology is consistently linked to a better knowledge of the structure of and functional interplay between biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, and proteins. Even though these building blocks of living matter display only aperiodic crystalline structure rather than systematic spatial order, it is well known that all the relevant biochemical processes follow precisely timed sequences, exhibiting a marked dynamical order. DNA or RNA-interacting proteins (e.g., helicases, polymerases, nucleases, recombinases, endonucleases) modulate essential transduction processes involving nucleic acids to achieve DNA duplication, repair, gene expression, and recombination, with such an astonishing efficiency that raises a fundamental question from a physical point of view. With biochemical reactions mostly being stereospecific, two (or more) reacting partners have to come in close contact and exhibit a definite spatial orientation to initiate particular reactions. So how do the various actors in a given biochemical process efficiently find each other? How does a protein effectively recruit the appropriate co-effector partner(s) or selectively connect with its DNA/RNA target(s) in a crowded cyto- or nucleo-plasmic environment? In other words, what are the physical forces that bring all these actors to the right place, in the right order, and in a reasonably narrow window of time to sustain cellular function and ultimately cellular life? The classical way to tackle these issues invokes Brownian motion or some variant, including proposals of so-called facilitated diffusion, but these alternative explanations are largely phenomenological and lack an underlying description of the physical forces involved. At physiological temperatures, ubiquitous water molecules undergo chaotic motion, colliding with larger and heavier components. The proposed outcome from simultaneous hits upon the latter is a force of both random intensity and direction. Hence, so Brownian reasoning goes, large molecules move in a diffusive way throughout the cellular spaces and sooner or later shall encounter their cognate partners. Many doubts arise when one tries to estimate diffusion-driven activation for some of the biochemical processes mentioned above. In fact, free diffusion is considerably slowed in the crowded cellular space [1]. Moreover, the discrepancy between the observed reaction rates in cells and the predictions of strict random diffusion modelling have been recently questioned [2–7]. On the other hand, for a long time it has been advocated that electrodynamic interactions acting at large distances can play an important role in bio-recognition by accelerating the encounters between cognate partners of biochemical reactions. These long-range electrodynamic interactions can be activated by different physical processes: *i*) many-body dispersion forces between two thin

parallel conducting cylinders [8–10] where an attractive force - of range much longer than the usual van der Waals R^{-6} one - arises from the correlation of current fluctuations within the cylinders; *ii*) between two neutral atoms, or small molecules, when one of the atoms is in an excited state and the transition frequencies of both atoms are similar [11]; *iii*) direct and inverse Hofmeister series for negatively or positively charged proteins, respectively, stemming from a complex interplay among dispersion forces, hydration, and ions in solution [12]; *iv*) resonant interactions between two molecules with oscillating large dipole moments entailed by collective intramolecular oscillations [13]. Long-range electrodynamic forces could help explaining a number of phenomena in living matter, such as the extraordinary efficiency of enzymatic reactions [14], comprising the molecular DNA transcription machinery, certain ligand-receptor recruitments, and so on [15, 16]. For both technological and theoretical reasons, no formal confirmation (or refutation) of this hypothesis of electrodynamic interactions between biomolecules has been validated until recently. After a thorough theoretical revisitation of Fröhlich’s theory [17], an experimental feasibility study [18, 19], and the experimental observation of out-of-equilibrium phonon condensation in model protein in aqueous solution [20] as a necessary condition [17] to activate intermolecular electrodynamic interactions, first experimental evidence of the activation of this kind of forces has been realized [21]. A recent molecular dynamics investigation with optically excited chromophores in a model protein in thermal equilibrium with the aqueous environment has demonstrated the complex interplay of chromophore, protein, and solvent degrees of freedom in producing the observed terahertz modes [22].

Within this newly opened field, there are several electrodynamic effects that are worth investigating, among the others there are many-body dispersion forces mentioned above under point (*i*), and a recent theoretical treatment of intermolecular interactions mediated by dipolar waves in the aqueous environment [26], however the aim of the present work is to adapt and combine the Resonant Recognition Model (RRM) [23, 25], detailed below, and the mentioned approach of Ref.[26]. This is in line with the attempt to understand whether intermolecular electrodynamic interactions are implicated under different conditions of activation, paying particular attention to resonance effects, which are crucial for selective recruitment of the cognate partners of a biochemical reaction.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section II the RRM is quickly sketched and applied to the interaction of the *EcoRI* restriction enzyme with an oligonucleotide (a 66-base-pair (bp) double-stranded DNA fragment) containing a cleavage sequence recognized by the enzyme. In Section III we define the model used to describe the electron motion along the DNA fragment

and the enzyme separately in the presence of phonons. Section IV contains the definition of the physical parameters used in the numerical simulations of the model equations. The results of these numerical simulations are then reported in Section V. The possibility of activating water-mediated DNA-*EcoRI* interaction through many-body dispersion and field theory approaches is discussed in Section VI. Finally, in Section VII some concluding remarks are made.

II. THE RESONANT RECOGNITION MODEL

The Resonant Recognition Model (RRM), first published in 1985 under the name Informational Spectrum Method (ISM) [23], is based on the idea that the informational content of nucleic acids (DNA and RNA) and of proteins has to be coded by the specific sequence of their components,— nucleotides or amino acids, respectively. Then the informational content of these macromolecules is taken into account by associating to a bio-macromolecule a numerical sequence of electron interaction potentials that depends on the specific sequence of nucleotides or amino acids. The reason for such a choice was motivated by the observation that a specific sequence of these interaction potentials correlates with some biological properties of organic molecules such as carcinogenicity, toxicity, antibiotic activity and so on [23]. These interaction potentials of nucleotides and amino acids were obtained on the basis of a general model pseudopotential [24]. Denoting by $x(m)$ the m -th member of a numerical series of electron-nucleotide, or electron-amino acid, interaction energy values relative to a DNA sequence or to a protein, its discrete Fourier transform is given by

$$X(n) = \sum_{m=0}^{N-1} x(m)e^{-i(2\pi/N)nm} , \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N/2 .$$

Then, let us denote by $Y(n)$ the coefficients of the discrete Fourier transform of a sequence referring to another biomolecule, and define the cross-spectrum as

$$S(n) = X(n)Y(n)^* , \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N/2$$

where $Y(n)^*$ denotes the complex conjugate of $Y(n)$. In this way, nucleotide or amino acid sequences are treated as discrete signals. The intriguing result is that the cross-spectrum, computed for two (or even more) sequences with similar biological functions and different primary structures, displays a well-defined peak frequency that correlates with the biological function. Then peak frequencies for different biological functions are different, and there is no peak frequency for random sequences. With the assumption that the points in the sequences are equidistant with

the dimensionless spacing $d = 1$, the maximal frequency in the spectrum is $f = 1/2d = 0.5$. Of course, this can be given a physical meaning by choosing physical units for d (with appropriate values for physical constants \hbar and c). The physical units of $S(n)$ are eV^2 or, equivalently Ry^2 , though cross-spectra are usually normalized to the maximum value to give $0 \leq S(n) \leq 1$.

This approach has been extensively developed [25, 28–30], showing that the RRM model is capable to calculate characteristic frequencies from periodicities within the distribution of energy of delocalized electrons along proteins, DNA, and/or RNA molecules using the charge velocity through these macromolecules. This concept has been applied to a number of biomacromolecular examples [25, 28–31], as well as in certain biomedical contexts including Crigler-Najjar syndrome [32], chronic pain [33], and the influence of ambient light on overall health [34]. This concept has been also experimentally tested by predicting the electromagnetic frequencies for activation of *L*-lactate dehydrogenase [35] and has been experimentally tested on photon emission from dying melanoma cells [36], on photon emission from lethal and non-lethal Ebola strains [37], as well as on differentiation of osteoblast s stem cells [38]. These findings could be used not only to understand biological processes and resonances in biomolecules, but also to influence and modulate these processes using either customized radiation profiles or *de novo* molecules and conductive particles.

A. The RRM applied to the DNA-*EcoRI* model

In order to make contact with the model considered in Refs.[26, 41], we have applied herein the RRM model to check the possible appearance of a peak frequency in the cross spectrum of the DNA-enzyme interaction between a 66-bp oligonucleotide containing a cleavage subsequence of the *EcoRI* enzyme and the *EcoRI* enzyme itself, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Top: DNA sequence of an oligonucleotide (66 base pairs) containing a target cleavage subsequence of the *EcoRI* enzyme. Bottom: Amino acid sequence of the *EcoRI* enzyme (entry 1QC9 from the Protein Data Bank).

Actually, with the RRM model it is possible to computationally analyze the interactions between amino acid sequences (proteins) and nucleotide sequences (DNA and RNA), based only on matching frequencies within the quasi-free electron energy distribution along these macromolecules. When we applied the RRM model to compare a 66-bp oligonucleotide containing a cleavage subsequence of the *EcoRI* enzyme and the *EcoRI* enzyme itself, we found a very strong common peak frequency at $f = 0.1699 \pm 0.0152$, indicating that this frequency is crucial for mutual interaction between the 66-bp oligonucleotide and the *EcoRI* enzyme, as presented in Figure 2. Interestingly, we have also found that the nucleotide pair C-G at position 33, which is within the cleavage site of the 66-bp oligonucleotide, significantly contributes to the RRM characteristic frequency at $f = 0.1699 \pm 0.0152$ and thus represents a "hot spot" [25, 28, 29] for this interaction. Furthermore, a charge moving through a biomolecular backbone can produce electromagnetic irradiation or absorption with spectral characteristics corresponding to energy distribution along the biomolecule. Thus physical frequency values that correspond to RRM frequencies depend on the velocities of charge through the macromolecular backbone. For the velocity $v = 7.87 \times 10^5 \text{m/s}$ as proposed in RRM works [25, 28, 29], the physical frequency values corresponding to $f = 0.1699 \pm 0.0152$ are given by $\nu = vf/2d$ so that, with $d = 3.8 \text{\AA}$, the physical frequency values belong to the interval between 160THz and 192THz.

Figure 2: Characteristic RRM frequency for mutual interaction between a 66-base-pair oligonucleotide and the *EcoRI* enzyme at $f = 0.1699 \pm 0.0152$. Physical frequency values corresponding to dimensionless f values are given by $\nu = vf/2d$.

However, for the velocity of $1.2 \times 10^5 \text{m/s}$ as proposed by Yomosa [39], the corresponding physical frequency for $f = 0.1699 \pm 0.0152$ would be between 24THz and 29THz, which is in accordance with the range of frequencies calculated in the following sections of this paper.

III. DEFINITION OF A DYNAMICAL MODEL AND ITS SOLUTION

In our recent work [40] we found a rich phenomenology of electron motion along DNA molecules under the action of an external source of energy. Depending on the initial electron excitation site and excitation energy, we saw the concentrated periodic motions of the electrons giving rise to a well-peaked frequency cross-spectrum of the electron current with a broadband noisy frequency spectrum. This motivated us strongly to interpret the Resonant Recognition Model (RRM) with the aid of explicit modeling of the electronic motions along the backbones of interacting DNA-protein complexes. In order to describe these electronic motions and their electrodynamic interactions we resort to a model partly borrowed from the standard Davydov and Holstein-Fröhlich models that have been originally introduced to account for electron-phonon interaction [42, 44, 45]. Thus, to model the electrons moving along a given DNA sequence and along the backbone of a DNA-interacting enzyme (e.g., the *EcoRI* restriction enzyme), separately, the

following common Hamiltonian operator for both *EcoRI* enzyme and DNA is assumed:

$$\hat{H} = \hat{H}_{el} + \hat{H}_{ph} + \hat{H}_{int}, \quad (1)$$

with

$$\hat{H}_{el} = \sum_{n=1}^N \left[E_0 \hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_n + \epsilon \langle \hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_n \rangle \hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_n + J_n (\hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_{n+1} + \hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_{n-1}) \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{H}_{ph} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_n \left[\frac{\hat{p}_n^2}{M_n} + \Omega_n (\hat{u}_{n+1} - \hat{u}_n)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu (\hat{u}_{n+1} - \hat{u}_n)^4 \right], \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{H}_{int} = \sum_n \chi_n (\hat{u}_{n+1} - \hat{u}_n) \hat{B}_n^\dagger \hat{B}_n, \quad (4)$$

in which \hat{H}_{el} and \hat{H}_{ph} are respectively the electronic and phononic Hamiltonians and \hat{H}_{int} indicates the electron-phonon interaction term. The coupling parameters are assumed dependent on the electron excitation site with respect to the site-independent case [46]. Considering only a longitudinal chain of amino acids (or nucleotides), \hat{B}_n and \hat{B}_n^\dagger denote the lowering and raising operators between the lattice site $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ labelling the amino acids along the *EcoRI* enzyme (or nucleotides along a DNA sequence). The parameter E_0 implies the initial excitation energy of the electron according to the initial form of the electronic state vector. The constant ϵ is the coupling energy of the interaction between the moving electron along the chain with the electrons of the substrate of amino acids (or nucleotides). The coupling parameter J_n is a site-dependent tunneling term of the moving electron across two nearest-neighboring amino acids (or nucleotides).

The momentum and position operators \hat{p}_n and \hat{u}_n of the vibronic Hamiltonian determine the longitudinal displacements of the n -th phonon in the sequence of amino acids (or nucleotides) from their equilibrium position, and the coupling term Ω_n denotes the site-dependent spring parameter of two neighboring sites. M_n is the mass of the n -th amino acid of the *EcoRI* enzyme sequence (or nucleotide of a DNA segment), and the anharmonic coupling constant μ implies phonon-phonon interaction, absent in the harmonic approximation. Finally, the parameter χ_n of the interaction Hamiltonian is the electron-phonon coupling dependent on the n -th site.

The wave function $|\psi(t)\rangle$ at any time t may be written in the Davydov ansatz by the following factorization:

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = |\Psi(t)\rangle |\Phi(t)\rangle, \quad (5)$$

with the normalization condition $\langle \psi(t) | \psi(t) \rangle = 1$. The state vector $|\Psi(t)\rangle$ describes a single quantum electronic excitation propagating along a protein chain of N amino acids (or a DNA

sequence of N nucleotides):

$$|\Psi(t)\rangle = \sum_n C_n(t) \hat{B}_n^\dagger |0\rangle_{el}, \quad (6)$$

in which $|0\rangle_{el}$ is the electronic vacuum state, and $|\Phi(t)\rangle$ is the vibronic wave function

$$|\Phi(t)\rangle = e^{-i/\hbar \sum [\beta_n(t) \hat{p}_n - \pi_n(t) \hat{u}_n]} |0\rangle_{ph}, \quad (7)$$

for which the expectation values for longitudinal displacement \hat{u}_n and momentum \hat{p}_n are respectively, $\langle \Phi | \hat{u}_n | \Phi \rangle = \beta_n(t)$ and $\langle \Phi | \hat{p}_n | \Phi \rangle = \pi_n(t)$. According to the time-dependent variation principle (TDVP), we define a phase factor ($S(t) \in \mathbb{R}$) and set a new wave function $|\phi(t)\rangle$ from Eq.(5) as $|\phi(t)\rangle = e^{iS(t)/\hbar} |\psi(t)\rangle$ satisfying the normalization $\langle \phi(t) | \phi(t) \rangle = 1$. Integrating the quantum Schrödinger equation, $i\hbar \langle \phi(t) | \partial_t | \phi(t) \rangle = \langle \phi(t) | \hat{H} | \phi(t) \rangle$ leads to $S(t) = \int_0^t L(t') dt'$ which can be associated with the classical Lagrangian of the system:

$$L(t) = i\hbar \langle \psi(t) | \partial_t | \psi(t) \rangle - \langle \psi(t) | \hat{H} | \psi(t) \rangle. \quad (8)$$

Now, equivalent to the least action principle, applying the TDVP gives us

$$\delta S(t) = \delta \int_0^t L(t') dt' = 0. \quad (9)$$

Then from the wave function (5) and Lagrangian (8) we have

$$L(t) = \sum_n \left\{ i\hbar \dot{C}_n(t) C_n^*(t) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\pi_n(t) \dot{\beta}_n(t) - \dot{\pi}_n(t) \beta_n(t) \right) - H(C_n, C_n^*, \beta_n, \pi_n) \right\}, \quad (10)$$

in which $H(C_n, C_n^*, \beta_n, \pi_n) = \langle \psi(t) | \hat{H} | \psi(t) \rangle$. Here we fulfill the stationary action (9) and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \delta S(t) = \int_0^t \sum_n \left\{ i\hbar \left(-\dot{C}_n^*(t) \delta C_n(t) + \dot{C}_n(t) \delta C_n^*(t) \right) + \dot{\beta}_n(t) \delta \pi_n(t) - \dot{\pi}_n(t) \delta \beta_n(t) \right. \\ \left. - (\partial_{C_n} H) \delta C_n - (\partial_{C_n^*} H) \delta C_n^* - (\partial_{\beta_n} H) \delta \beta_n - (\partial_{\pi_n} H) \delta \pi_n \right\} dt = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

which gives the equations

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar \dot{C}_n &= \partial_{C_n^*} H \\ \dot{\beta}_n &= \partial_{\pi_n} H \\ \dot{\pi}_n &= -\partial_{\beta_n} H. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

According to the expectation value of the Hamiltonian

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi | \hat{H} | \psi \rangle = \sum_n & \left[E_0 |C_n|^2 + \epsilon |C_n|^4 + J_n (C_n^* C_{n+1} + C_{n+1}^* C_n) \right. \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{M_n} \pi_n^2 + \Omega_n (\beta_{n+1} - \beta_n)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu (\beta_{n+1} - \beta_n)^4 \right) \\ & \left. + \chi_n (\beta_{n+1} - \beta_n) |C_n|^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

and Eqs. (12), the equations of motion are found:

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar \dot{C}_n &= \left(E_0 + 2\epsilon |C_n|^2 + \chi_n (\beta_{n+1} - \beta_n) \right) C_n + J_n C_{n+1} + J_{n-1} C_{n-1}, \\ M_n \ddot{\beta}_n &= \Omega_n \beta_{n+1} + \Omega_{n-1} \beta_{n-1} - \Omega_{n-1} \beta_n - \Omega_n \beta_n + \chi_n |C_n|^2 - \chi_{n-1} |C_{n-1}|^2 \\ &+ \mu \left((\beta_{n+1} - \beta_n)^3 - (\beta_n - \beta_{n-1})^3 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

It is worth noting that the dynamical equations worked out by means of the TDVP are formally classical but give the time evolution of actual quantum expectation values.

IV. PHYSICAL PARAMETERS FOR THE NUMERICAL COMPUTATIONS

We need to determine the authentic physical values of the coupling parameters of the Hamiltonian to perform our numerical simulations. In so doing, we borrow the quantities from Refs. [24, 47] of the potential interaction energies between an electron and each of the twenty amino acids reported in Table 1, as well as the potential interaction energies between an electron and each of the four nucleotides presented in Table 2.

During its route, the moving electron with initial energy E_0 experiences a periodic sequence of square potential barriers of different heights and of the same width a — the average distance between two nearest neighboring sites (the standard notation a is the same of d of Section II). — by tunneling across the chain of amino acids constituting a protein, or across the sequence of nucleotides composing DNA. Such a distance is $a = 4.5\text{\AA}$ and $a = 3.4\text{\AA}$, respectively, in the *EcoRI* enzyme and DNA fragment. Then we can estimate roughly the electron tunneling term as $J_n = E_0 T_{n,n+1}$ by introducing the transmission coefficient $T_{n,n+1}$ from the probability $P(n \rightarrow n \pm 1)$ of tunneling from one potential well to the nearest one as follows [48]:

Amino acid	EAIP (Ry)	EAIP (eV)	Amino acid	EAIP (Ry)	EAIP (eV)
Leu	0.0000	0.0000	Tyr	0.0516	0.7017
Ile	0.0000	0.0000	Trp	0.0548	0.7452
Asn	0.0036	0.0489	Gln	0.0761	1.0349
Gly	0.0050	0.0680	Met	0.0823	1.1192
Val	0.0057	0.0775	Ser	0.0829	1.1274
Glu	0.0058	0.0788	Cys	0.0829	1.1274
Pro	0.0198	0.2692	Thr	0.0941	1.2797
His	0.0242	0.3291	Phe	0.0946	1.2865
Lys	0.0371	0.5045	Arg	0.0959	1.3042
Ala	0.0373	0.5072	Asp	0.1263	1.7176

Table 1: Electron- amino acid interaction potential (EAIP) values for 20 amino acids , reproduced from Ref. [47].

Nucleotide	ENIP (Ry)	ENIP (eV)	Nucleotide	ENIP (Ry)	ENIP (eV)
A	0.1260	1.7143	T	0.1335	1.8164
G	0.0806	1.0966	C	0.1340	1.8232

Table 2: Electron- nucleotide interaction potential (ENIP) values for nucleotides adenine (A), thymine (T), guanine (G), and cytosine (C) , reproduced from Ref. [47].

- Case 1: $E_0 < E_{n+1}$

$$T_{n,n+1} = \left[1 + \frac{E_{n+1}^2 \sinh^2(\beta_{n+1}a)}{4E_0(E_{n+1} - E_0)} \right]^{-1}, \quad (15)$$

where $\beta_{n+1} = [2m_e(E_{n+1} - E_0)/\hbar^2]^{1/2}$;

- Case 2: $E_0 > E_{n+1}$

$$T_{n,n+1} = \left[1 + \frac{E_{n+1}^2 \sin^2(\beta_{n+1}a)}{4E_0(E_0 - E_{n+1})} \right]^{-1}, \quad (16)$$

in which $\beta_{n+1} = [2m_e(E_0 - E_{n+1})/\hbar^2]^{1/2}$;

with, of course, $E_0 \neq E_{n+1}$. Here m_e is the electron mass, and E_{n+1} are the potential interaction energies between the moving electron and the sequence of amino acids (or nucleotides) given in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Moreover, as a rough estimate we set $\chi_n = dE/dx = (E_{n+1} - E_n)/a$ as the site-dependent electron-phonon coupling.

In order to perform the numerical simulations, the dimensionless expectation value of the Hamiltonian in Eq. (13) and the dimensionless equations of motion (14) are found by rescaling time $t/\tau = \omega^{-1}$, where t and $\omega^{-1} = 0.1$ ps have units of time, and rescaling distance $\beta_n/b_n = L$, where β_n and $L = (\hbar\omega^{-1}M_n^{-1})^{1/2}$ have units of length. Then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi | \hat{H} | \psi \rangle = & \sum_n \left[E' |C_n|^2 + \epsilon' |C_n|^4 + J'_n (C_n^* C_{n+1} + C_{n+1}^* C_n) \right. \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\dot{b}_n^2 + \Omega'_n (b_{n+1} - b_n)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu' (b_{n+1} - b_n)^4 \right) \\ & \left. + \chi'_n (b_{n+1} - b_n) |C_n|^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} i \frac{dC_n}{d\tau} &= \left(E' + 2\epsilon' |C_n|^2 + \chi'_n (b_{n+1} - b_n) \right) C_n + J'_n C_{n+1} + J'_{n-1} C_{n-1}, \\ \frac{d^2 b_n}{d\tau^2} &= \Omega'_n b_{n+1} + \Omega'_{n-1} b_{n-1} - \Omega'_{n-1} b_n - \Omega'_n b_n + \chi'_n |C_n|^2 - \chi'_{n-1} |C_{n-1}|^2 \\ &+ \mu' \left[(b_{n+1} - b_n)^3 - (b_n - b_{n-1})^3 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where the dimensionless parameters are

$$\begin{aligned} E' &= \frac{E_0}{\hbar\omega}; & \epsilon' &= \frac{\epsilon}{\hbar\omega}; & J'_n &= \frac{J_n}{\hbar\omega}; \\ \chi'_n &= \frac{\chi_n}{\sqrt{\hbar M_n \omega^3}}; & \Omega'_n &= \frac{\Omega_n}{M_n \omega^2}; & \mu' &= \frac{\mu \hbar}{M_n^2 \omega^3}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The speed of sound in proteins is $v \sim 4$ km/s [42, 50] and in nucleic acids is $v \sim 1.69$ km/s [49], neglecting small local variations due to the different masses of the amino acids or the nucleotides, respectively. We apply two different analyses for computing the spring parameter in our simulations. First, we consider the known speed of sound $v = a(\Omega_n/M_n)^{1/2}$ leading to the constant dimensionless parameter $\Omega' = v^2/a^2\omega^2$ from Eq. (19), where $\Omega' = 0.79$ for amino acids and $\Omega' = 0.25$ for nucleotides. Second, from Ref. [42] we borrow the spring constant of amino acids $\Omega = 18.3$ N/m, giving us from Eq. (19) the dimensionless site-dependent parameter $\Omega'_n = 1.83/m_n$ where $m_n = M_n\omega^2$. Third, we assume the average spring constant $\Omega = v^2\langle M \rangle/a^2$ of DNA, where $\langle M \rangle$ is the arithmetic average mass of the nucleotides, to acquire the corresponding dimensionless site-dependent parameter $\Omega'_n = 0.48/m_n$ for nucleotides. $\mu' = 0.5$ in our numerical investigations.

In order to perform numerical integration of the dynamical equations it is useful to introduce the variables

$$q_n = \frac{C_n + C_n^*}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad p_n = \frac{C_n - C_n^*}{i\sqrt{2}}, \quad (20)$$

so we can rewrite Eqs. (18) as

$$\dot{q}_n = \left[E' + \frac{\epsilon'}{2}(q_n^2 + p_n^2) + \chi'(b_{n+1} - b_n) \right] p_n + J'_n p_{n+1} + J'_{n-1} p_{n-1}, \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{p}_n = - \left[E' + \frac{\epsilon'}{2}(q_n^2 + p_n^2) + \chi'(b_{n+1} - b_n) \right] q_n + J'_n q_{n+1} + J'_{n-1} q_{n-1}, \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{b}_n &= \Omega'(b_{n+1} + b_{n-1} - 2b_n) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\chi'_n (q_n^2 + p_n^2) - \chi'_{n-1} (q_{n-1}^2 + p_{n-1}^2) \right) \\ &+ \mu' \left[(b_{n+1} - b_n)^3 - (b_n - b_{n-1})^3 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Substituting the right-hand side of Eq. (23) above with $\mathcal{B}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)]$ gives $b_n(t + \Delta t) = 2b_n(t) - b_n(t - \Delta t) + (\Delta t)^2 \mathcal{B}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)]$; therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{b}_n &= \pi'_n \\ \dot{\pi}'_n &= \mathcal{B}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)]. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Furthermore, we substitute $\mathcal{Q}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)]$ and $\mathcal{P}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)]$, respectively, with the right-hand sides of Eqs. (21) and (22) in order to numerically integrate. This integration is accomplished by combining a finite differences scheme and a leap-frog scheme as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} q_n(t + \Delta t) &= q_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{Q}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)], \\ p_n(t + \Delta t) &= p_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{P}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)], \\ b_n(t + \Delta t) &= b_n(t) + \Delta t \pi'_n(t), \\ \pi'_n(t + \Delta t) &= \pi'_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{B}_n[\mathbf{b}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{q}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{p}(t + \Delta t)]. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The integration scheme for $b_n(t)$ and the associated adimensional momenta $\pi'_n(t)$ is a symplectic one, meaning that all the Poincaré invariants of the associated Hamiltonian flow are conserved, one of these invariants is energy [43]. We cannot apply the simple leap-frog scheme to the equations for $\dot{q}_n(t)$ and $\dot{p}_n(t)$ because the right-hand side of equations in (21) for $\dot{q}_n(t)$ explicitly depend on $q_n(t)$ and $b_n(t)$; therefore, we integrate the first two equations in (25) with an Euler predictor-corrector scheme to arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} q_n^{(0)}(t + \Delta t) &= q_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{Q}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)], \\ p_n^{(0)}(t + \Delta t) &= p_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{P}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)], \\ q_n^{(1)}(t + \Delta t) &= q_n(t) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)] + \mathcal{Q}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}^{(0)}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{p}^{(0)}(t + \Delta t)] \right\}, \\ p_n^{(1)}(t + \Delta t) &= p_n(t) + \frac{\Delta t}{2} \left\{ \mathcal{P}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}(t), \mathbf{p}(t)] + \mathcal{P}_n[\mathbf{b}(t), \mathbf{q}^{(0)}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{p}^{(0)}(t + \Delta t)] \right\}, \\ b_n(t + \Delta t) &= b_n(t) + \Delta t \pi'_n(t), \\ \pi'_n(t + \Delta t) &= \pi'_n(t) + \Delta t \mathcal{B}_n[\mathbf{b}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{q}^{(1)}(t + \Delta t), \mathbf{p}^{(1)}(t + \Delta t)]. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The integration of half of the set of the dynamical equations (25) by means of a symplectic algorithm, and half of the equations by means of the Euler predictor-corrector scheme (26) results in the conservation of total energy without any shift —only zero-mean fluctuations around a given value fixed by the initial conditions— the fluctuations being able to be arbitrarily reduced by considering sufficiently small integration time steps Δt .

We need also to define the initial states of the electron and phonon independently of the specific physical excitation mechanism. The electron wavefunction in Eq. (6) is described by the amplitudes $C_n(t)$ centered at the excitation site $n = n_0$ and distributed at time $t = 0$ [42] as

$$C_n(t = 0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8\sigma_0}} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{n - n_0}{4\sigma_0}\right) \quad (27)$$

where σ_0 specifies the amplitude width. Concerning the phonon part of the system, we consider a thermalized *EcoRI* enzyme and DNA fragment at physiological temperature $T = 310$ K. At thermal equilibrium, average kinetic and potential energies per degree of freedom are equal, and the total energy is equally shared among all the phonon modes. Accordingly, the displacements and the associated velocities have been initialized with random values of zero-mean at $t = 0$. Then in a dimensionless form we have

$$\langle |b_n(0)| \rangle_n = \sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{\hbar\omega\Omega'}}; \quad \langle |\pi'_n(0)| \rangle_n = \sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{\hbar\omega}}. \quad (28)$$

Periodic boundary conditions have been used for both the electron and phonon parts of the DNA-*EcoRI* interacting system, and the characteristic frequency $\omega = 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$ has been employed.

A-priori we can wonder if and to what extent thermodynamic effects can influence the behavior of the system under investigation. Taking into account thermodynamic effects would require coupling the system with a heat bath. In so doing energy fluctuations would be induced in the system. Now, the average thermal energy $k_B T$ at physiological temperature ($T = 310\text{K}$) is ~ 27 meV, much smaller than the electron-nucleotides and electron-amino acid interaction energies which, for the four nucleotides, range from 1.1 to 1.8 eV and which, for amino-acids, range from 0.5 eV to 1.7 eV, with a few exceptions: the Asn - electron interaction energy $\simeq 0.05$ eV, and Gly, Val, Glu - electron interaction energy $\simeq 0.07$ eV, in any case approximately twice and three times the thermal energy, respectively. Thus we can reasonably assume that thermodynamic effects cannot qualitatively alter the outcomes of our model. Moreover, we considered thermalized macromolecules *EcoRI* enzyme and DNA fragment at physiological temperature $T = 310\text{K}$ - by

initializing the velocities of amino acids and nucleotides with random values under the conditions of Eq. (28) - meaning that a noisy background in the dynamics of the subunits of the molecules is already present and reasonably replaces the random perturbations due to the coupling with a heat bath.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We have used an integration time step $\Delta t = 5 \times 10^{-6}$ to work out our numerical simulations under very good energy conservation with a typical relative error $\Delta E/E = 10^{-6}$. The following analyses report the spectral properties of electron currents in the interaction of a DNA fragment of $N = 66$ nucleotides (sequence in the 3'-5' direction shown in Fig. 1, top panel) and an *EcoRI* restriction enzyme of $N = 276$ amino acids (sequence shown in Fig. 1, bottom panel) for the different initial activation energies E_0 of the electron, the various initial electronic excitation sites n_0 of the probability amplitude in Eq. (27), and the distinct forms of the phononic spring term Ω_n . We study the discrete Fourier spectra of the electron currents activated on a segment of DNA nucleotides and also on an amino acid sequence of the DNA-interacting enzyme, separately. We will use the indices 1 and 2 for all the terms of DNA and *EcoRI*, respectively. Resorting to the standard probability current $j(x, t)$ of the electron wavefunction in Eq. (6), the electron density current is given by

$$j(x, t) = \frac{e\hbar}{2m_e i} (\psi^* \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \psi^*).$$

Hence the average electron current, in a spatially discretized form for numerical computation, is

$$\begin{aligned} i_{1,2}(t) &= \frac{1}{l_{1,2}} \int_0^{l_{1,2}} j_{1,2}(x, t) dx = \frac{e\hbar}{2N_{1,2}a_{1,2}m_e i} \\ &\times \sum_{j=1}^{N_{1,2}} \left(\Psi_{1,2}^*(x_j, t) \frac{\Psi_{1,2}(x_{j+1}, t) - \Psi_{1,2}(x_{j-1}, t)}{2} \right. \\ &\left. - \Psi_{1,2}(x_j, t) \frac{\Psi_{1,2}^*(x_{j+1}, t) - \Psi_{1,2}^*(x_{j-1}, t)}{2} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $l_{1,2}$ are the sequence lengths and $i_{1,2}$ are the currents flowing along the DNA fragment and the *EcoRI* enzyme, respectively. In Figs. (3), (4), (5), and (6), we have plotted the cross frequency spectra of the two currents $\tilde{i}_1^*(\nu)\tilde{i}_2(\nu)$ and studied whether the recognition sites CTTAAG of DNA, which are cleaved by the *EcoRI* enzyme, manifest specific currents that play a decisive role in the DNA-protein interaction.

Fig. (3) shows the behavior of the system when the excited electron on the DNA has the initial energy $E_{1,0} = 0.72$ eV and its wavefunction is initially centered at the site $n_{1,0} = N_1/2$, while for the restriction enzyme the initial excitation energy of the electron is $E_{2,0} = 0.2$ eV with wavefunction initially centered at $n_{2,0} = N_2/3$. As discussed in Section IV, we consider the dimensionless expressions of the site-dependent phononic springs $\Omega'_{1,n} = 0.48/m_n$ for the nucleotides and of the constant term $\Omega'_2 = 0.79$ for the amino acids. In panel (3)a we see a clear co-resonance around 20 THz when the specific CTTAAG restriction sequence is taken into account. This result is in qualitative agreement with the peak found by applying the RRM. Another significant finding shown in panel (3)b is that the cross spectrum becomes significantly more spread (“noisier”) when the recognition sites are chosen as the cyclic permutation AGCTTA. Moreover, in panel (3)c when we exchange just one nucleotide of the target DNA sequence with its base-pair complement, resulting in CATAAG, the co-resonance is altered slightly. By similarly changing two nucleotides of the target sequence to arrive at GTTAAC in panel (3)d, the co-resonance is markedly suppressed, as additional peaks emerge, and with significant broadening, bearing a close resemblance to panel (3)b.

In Fig. (4) we assume the same substrates and initial conditions of Fig. (3) and evaluate the cross frequency spectra with other substitutions of nucleotides in the target DNA restriction site. Again comparing with the sharp co-resonant frequency in panel (3)a, panel (4)a shows the pronounced suppression of co-resonance by randomizing the target DNA recognition sites to TCATGA. Analogously to Fig. (3), a one-nucleotide change to CTTAAC in panel (4)b and a two-nucleotide change to CATATG in panel (4)c are shown to entail the pronounced suppression of co-resonance.

Fig. (5) confirms well the robustness of the phenomenology presented in Figures (3) and (4), as the results are obtained for different initial conditions. Here we assume the initial electronic activation energy $E_{1,0} = 0.85$ eV is deposited at the site $n_{1,0} = N_1/2$ in the DNA sequence, and $E_{2,0} = 0.85$ eV at $n_{2,0} = N_2/3$ in the *EcoRI* enzyme. Also, the dimensionless parameter of the phononic springs in DNA is assumed constant $\Omega'_1 = 0.25$ and in *EcoRI* enzyme is considered site-dependent with $\Omega'_{2,n} = 1.83/m_n$. The sharp co-resonant peak of the DNA-*EcoRI* interaction with the canonical restriction site CTTAAG is depicted in panel (5)a and occurs around 29 THz. The spectrum in panel (5)b is broadened significantly by randomizing the target recognition sites to TCATGA and lacks the co-resonance peak. Whereas it is clear in panel (5)c that the sharply peaked frequency spectrum changes very little by replacing only one nucleotide with its base-

pair complement, resulting in CTTATG, and also when two nucleotides are replaced, resulting in CTATAG, as displayed in panel (5)d.

Fig. (6) shows the same initial conditions of Fig. (5) but with different arrangements of nucleotides in the DNA recognition sites. Taking the randomized sequence AGATCT in panel (6)a broadens the co-resonance spectrum of the panel (5)a, but neither a one-nucleotide replacement with its base-pair complement to CATAAG in panel (6)b nor a two-nucleotide replacement to CATAAC in panel (6)c, significantly alters the cross-frequency spectrum.

In Fig. (7) we consider the same initial conditions and substrate of Fig. (3) and evaluate the cross frequency spectrum after replacing *EcoRI* with another type II restriction endonuclease, i.e. *EcoRV*. *EcoRV* has been proved to recognize and cleave the palindromic six-base-pair DNA sequence CTATAG [61], which is not contained in the substrate so far considered. Comparing with the sharp co-resonant frequency in panel (3)a, one observes a complete broadening of the spectrum.

Using again the same initial conditions and substrate of Fig. (3), we finally evaluate the cross-frequency spectrum upon single point mutations on *EcoRI* primary sequence instead of considering rearrangements of the nucleotide sequence of the cleaving site on DNA. The data are reported in Appendix A.

Figure 3: Cross frequency spectra between a DNA strand with $N_1 = 66$ nucleotides and the *EcoRI* enzyme with $N_2 = 276$ amino acids for the following initial conditions: $T = 310$ K, $n_{1,0} = N_1/2$, $n_{2,0} = N_2/3$, $E'_{1,0} = 110$, $E'_{2,0} = 30$, $\epsilon'_1 = \epsilon'_2 = 5$, $\mu'_1 = \mu'_2 = 0.5$, $\Omega'_2 = 0.79$ and site-dependent parameters $\Omega_{1,n} = 0.48/m_n$, $J'_{1,n}$, $J'_{2,n}$, $\chi'_{1,n}$ and $\chi'_{2,n}$ corresponding to $E_{1,0} = 0.72$ eV, $E_{2,0} = 0.2$ eV, $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 = 0.0329$ eV, $\Omega_2 = v_2^2 \langle M \rangle / a_2^2$, $\Omega_{1,n} = v_1^2 M_n / a_1^2$, $J_{1,n}$, $J_{2,n}$, $\chi_{1,n}$ and $\chi_{2,n}$ consistent with Eqs. (15), (16), (19), and related main text; and $\sigma_{1,0} = \sigma_{2,0} = 0.1$. Panels show DNA strand containing a) the canonical target CTTAAG recognition site, b) cyclic permutation of restriction site in a) to AGCTTA, c) one-nucleotide change from a) with its base-pair complement to CATAAG, and d) two-nucleotide change from a) with their base-pair complements to GTTAAC.

Figure 4: Cross frequency spectra between a DNA strand and the *EcoRI* enzyme, under the same substrate and initial conditions of Fig. 3. Panels show DNA strand containing: a) randomized restriction site TCATGA; b) one-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to CTTAAC; c) two-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to CATATG.

Figure 5: Cross frequency spectra between a DNA strand with $N_1 = 66$ nucleotides and the *EcoRI* enzyme with $N_2 = 276$ amino acids for the following initial conditions: $n_{1,0} = N_1/2$, $n_{2,0} = N_2/3$, $E'_{1,0} = E'_{2,0} = 129.17$, $\Omega'_1 = 0.25$, $\Omega'_{2,n} = 1.83/m_n$ corresponding to $E_{1,0} = E_{2,0} = 0.85$ eV, $\Omega_1 = v_1^2 \langle M \rangle / a_1^2$ and $\Omega_{2,n} = v_2^2 M_n / a_2^2$. The other parameters are the same as in Fig. (3). Panels show DNA strand containing: a) the canonical target CTTAAG recognition site; b) a randomized restriction site TCATGA; c) a one-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to CTTATG; d) a two-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to CTATAG.

Figure 6: Cross frequency spectra between a DNA strand and the *EcoRI* enzyme, under the same substrate and initial conditions of Fig. 5. Panels show DNA strand containing a e) randomized restriction site AGATCT, f) one-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to CATAAG, g) two-nucleotide change from the canonical target CTTAAG to GTTATG.

Figure 7: Cross frequency spectrum between the original substrate, containing the CTTAAG sequence recognised by *EcoRI*, and *EcoRV* enzyme, under the same initial conditions of Figure 3.

VI. POSSIBLE MECHANISMS MEDIATING LONG-RANGE DNA-PROTEIN INTERACTIONS

The results reported in the preceding section highlight the potential origin of selective electrodynamic interactions between DNA and protein. In order to assess the actual relevance of the co-resonance of electron currents in biological contexts, a quantitative estimate of the strength of the implied interaction requires a similar strategy to the one reported analytically in [17], as well as additional experimental data on the intensity of the currents and the possible mechanisms of their activation in a biological environment. These points will be tackled in future investigations, but in what follows we sketch possible scenarios that support electrodynamic mediation of DNA-protein interactions.

First, given two electron currents $j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $j^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ representing those of DNA and *EcoRI*, respectively,

$$\vec{j}^{(1,2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{e\hbar}{2m_e i} \left(\psi^* \vec{\nabla} \psi - \psi \vec{\nabla} \psi^* \right)$$

and according to the D'Alembert equations (in Gaussian units and Lorenz gauge),

$$\square^2 \vec{A}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (4\pi/c) \vec{j}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

and

$$\square^2 \vec{A}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (4\pi/c) \vec{j}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t),$$

the mutual interaction is described by the coupling terms

$$\vec{j}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \vec{A}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{j}^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \vec{A}^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t) .$$

Since the D'Alembert equation is linear, the vector potential inherits the spectral properties of the current that generates it. As a consequence, the co-resonance between the two currents $j^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $j^{(2)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ entails the largest values of the time averages of the interaction energies.

Second, intriguing connections exist between the models presented above, which describe electronic motions along a given DNA sequence and a given protein sequence, and the coordinated electronic fluctuations that arise from van der Waals many-body dispersion forces [26, 52–54] in a variety of molecular contexts. Specifically, productive insights have emerged from attempts to unify atomistic, continuum, and mean-field treatments in the quantum electronic behaviors of DNA and proteins in water [26, 54–57]. Even in the presence of thermally turbulent aqueous environments, it has been shown that these collective electronic dispersion correlations can persist at

several nanometers from the protein-water interface, and these correlations are energetically relevant for protein-folding processes at the microsecond scale [56], and likely for even longer times *in vivo*.

Kurian and coworkers [26, 52] have additionally shown that such collective electronic (quantum harmonic oscillator) modes are suitably fine-tuned for the synchronized catalysis of two phosphodiester bonds (~ 0.46 eV), and that the palindromic mirror symmetry of the double-stranded DNA target sequence recognized by the enzyme (see Figure 8) allows for conservation of parity in the symmetric, site-specific cleavage of both DNA strands. By considering the radiative field \mathbf{E} created by the collective electronic fluctuation modes in the DNA target sequence, a nonvanishing polarization density emerges spontaneously in the orientational correlations of the water dipole network through the interaction Hamiltonian $H = -\mathbf{d}_e \cdot \mathbf{E}$, where \mathbf{d}_e is the permanent electric dipole moment for a single water molecule.

Following standard treatments in quantum optics [58], this interaction between the DNA radiative field and the surrounding (quasi-continuous) water dipole field can be written in the form of a Jaynes-Cummings-like Hamiltonian that scales with the number of water molecules N as

$$H_{\text{int}} = \hbar\sqrt{N}\gamma(a^\dagger S^- + aS^+), \quad (30)$$

where γ is the coupling constant proportional to the matrix element of the molecular dipole moment and inversely proportional to the volume square root, a^\dagger and a are the creation and annihilation operators, respectively, for the DNA radiative electric field \mathbf{E} , and S^+ and S^- are the raising and lowering operators, respectively, for the collective water dipole state. The quasi-continuum water dipole “field” thus takes the place of the N two-level systems described in the Tavis-Cummings model [59].

It should be noted that the coupling $\sqrt{N}\gamma$ in Equation (30) between the DNA radiative field and the collective water orientational state levels [26] scales with the square root of the water density ρ , which varies with temperature and pressure. However, if we consider that the number of water molecules in a (cubic) domain encompassed by infrared wavelengths $\gtrsim 1 \mu\text{m}$ exceeds 10 billion, such sufficiently large N for the collective state can provide a protective gap against thermalization ($k_B T \approx 0.02$ eV at physiological temperatures) for the long-range correlations we consider. Furthermore, the spontaneous breakdown of phase symmetry generates a field polarization (in the so-called “limit cycle” regime) that preserves gauge invariance by dynamical coherence between the matter quasi-continuum field (DNA, water, enzyme) and the phase-locked electromagnetic

Figure 8: (Color online) Aromatic network in *EcoRI*-DNA complex. Tryptophan (blue), tyrosine (purple), and phenylalanine (green) form correlated electronic dispersion networks in *EcoRI*, shown here in the top panel bound to its double-stranded DNA substrate, with adenine-thymine (yellow) and cytosine-guanine (orange) base pairs highlighted. Other amino acids (gray) are displayed in the context of their secondary structures within the enzyme, and in the bottom panel only one of the two *EcoRI* dimers is shown for clarity, to showcase the $\pi - \pi$ stacking of the DNA bases. Image of *EcoRI* (entry 1CKQ from the Protein Data Bank) at 1.85 Å resolution created with PyMOL and adapted from [26].

field (radiative field from DNA, water, enzyme).

As a toy model, we use Faraday's law of induction for the DNA double helix, considered here as a long solenoid with radius R , n turns per unit length, and current along the backbone varying as $I = I_0 e^{-\alpha t}$, where α is in general complex. For distances from the longitudinal axis $r > R$ outside the helix-solenoid, we can estimate the induced electric field $\mathbf{E}(r, t)$ tangent to a circular path surrounding the cylindrically symmetric system:

$$|\mathbf{E}(r, t)| = \frac{\Omega}{2} \frac{|e^{-\alpha t}|}{r}, \quad (31)$$

where $\Omega = |\alpha|\mu n I_0 R^2$ and μ is the magnetic permeability in water. From Equation (31) we can thus derive the creation and annihilation operators a^\dagger, a for the radiative field in the interaction Hamiltonian of Equation (30).

The resulting interaction energies range between $\sim 0.1 - 1$ eV, populating bands in the infrared spectrum between $0 < \nu < 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which overlaps with the energy scale of the collective electronic fluctuation modes in the DNA target sequence and in the enzyme when taken separately, but remains distinct from the more energetic intramolecular vibrations and purely electronic transitions of individual water molecules. These collective electronic fluctuation modes in the $0.1 - 1$ eV range do not couple to the rotational quantum transitions of individual water dipoles (meV scale), but rather to the emergent polarization modes present in the collective dipole network. The spectroscopic peaks for liquid water also lie completely within this range.

Chiral sum frequency generation spectroscopy experiments [60] have demonstrated the existence of a chiral water superstructure surrounding DNA under ambient conditions, thereby confirming that the chiral structure of DNA can be imprinted electrodynamically on the surrounding solvent. These experiments have also shown that some sequence-specific fine structure persists in this chiral spine of hydration, providing a mediating context for DNA target sequence recognition by various proteins.

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The aim of the present paper is twofold. First, we put forward a novel physical interpretation for the resonant recognition model (RRM) of biomolecular interactions, emerging from a widely used electron-phonon Hamiltonian applied to alternating currents along the backbone of specific DNA target sequences in the second quantization framework. Second, the work here reported contributes to the still open discussion of long-distance electrodynamic intermolecular interactions, which have recently been demonstrated experimentally [21, 27].

Regarding the first aim, the second-quantized RRM was applied to the pair of partners of the biochemical reaction involving a DNA fragment and a restriction enzyme, *EcoRI*, which binds to a specific target subsequence of the DNA fragment to cleave it. The interaction energies of an electron with the sequence of nucleotides composing a specific DNA fragment on the one side, and the interaction energies of an electron with the sequence of amino acids composing the *EcoRI* enzyme on the other side, yield two numerical sequences. The product of their discrete Fourier

spectra, or cross-spectrum, displays a sharp co-resonance peak. The peak so found qualitatively witnesses to the specific relationship between the two biomolecules, though the physics behind this co-resonance still needs to be clarified. Such a clarification is provided by the co-resonance of the time-domain Fourier spectra of the alternating electron currents moving along the DNA and enzyme, respectively. These currents are worked out through second quantization dynamical models describing the electron-phonon coupling, which are derived from standard Davydov and Holstein-Fröhlich treatments [42, 44, 45]. The remarkable finding is the disappearance of the co-resonance peak of the cross-spectrum when the six-base-pair target recognition subsequence CTTAAG on the DNA is randomized in different ways or when the primary sequence of *EcoRI* is replaced by the one of *EcoRV*, while keeping the DNA substrate recognized by *EcoRI*. Furthermore, preliminary test on *EcoRI* mutants with single point mutations, yield a modulation in the co-resonance response coherent with experimental data.

Regarding the second aim of the paper, the prospective relevance for biology of long-range selective and attractive intermolecular interactions was discussed in the Introduction and has recently been given experimental confirmation [21] in the presence of collective intramolecular oscillations. The question naturally arises whether the electronic degrees of freedom of electro-dynamically interacting molecules can offer alternative or complementary mechanisms to activate such long-range intermolecular forces. We have presented a first step in this second direction, and the remarkable finding mentioned above motivates further investigations. In fact, at present we have considered the motion of a single electron, but we can think that under suitable excitation processes (for example, under repeated ATP hydrolysis events or near an ionic channel) definitely stronger currents can be activated, producing either direct electrodynamic current-to-current interactions, or, as intriguingly proposed in [26] and discussed in the preceding section, water-mediated electro-dynamical interactions between the radiative field emerging from electronic fluctuational motions in DNA and in protein, and the water dipole (matter) field in the quasi-continuum limit. Finally, the observed sequence-dependent co-resonance phenomenology for the chosen biochemical model is suggestive of a potentially rich variety of selective electrodynamic interactions of a more general kind, including, for example, those between DNA molecules and transcription factors undergoing electron-phonon excitation.

VIII. DATA AVAILABILITY

The Matlab scripts used to produce the data sets of the current study are available at [10.5281/zenodo.10593456](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10593456).

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Appendix A

To further assess the coherence of the model, we evaluate the cross frequency spectrum between the substrate and *EcoRI*, upon single point mutations on the primary sequence of the protein. Using the same initial conditions of Fig. 3, we specifically test the mutations $Ala^{138} \rightarrow Thr$, $Glu^{192} \rightarrow Lys$, $His^{114} \rightarrow Tyr$, and $Asp^{91} \rightarrow Asn$, where $x^y \rightarrow z$ indicates that the amino acid x at position y in the primary sequence of the protein has been replaced by the amino acid z . The first three mutations, belonging to the group of the so-called promiscuous mutations, have been proved to produce mutants able to bind both the cognate sequence CTTAAG and miscognate sites (differing by a single base-pair from the canonical one) [62], whilst the last mutation has been shown to essentially reduce the catalytic activity of *EcoRI* [63]. Panels a,b,c of Fig. 9 show that the promiscuous mutations still yield a sharp co-resonant peak. On the contrary, the mutation $Asp^{91} \rightarrow Asn$ produces a sizeable decrease of the peak (panel d of Fig. 9). These findings are coherent with the experimental data.

Figure 9: Cross frequency spectra between the original substrate and the *EcoRI* mutants with the single point mutations; a) $Ala^{138} \rightarrow Thr$; b) $Glu^{192} \rightarrow Lys$; c) $His^{114} \rightarrow Tyr$; and d) $Asp^{91} \rightarrow Asn$. The initial conditions are the same of Figure 3.

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